

The Substance That Forms the Electric Field

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Abstract

This paper uses a refractive index formula to predict the number of outer electrons of chlorine atoms, and then uses the refractive index data of HCl to verify it. The source of error is less than 10ppm, proves that the refractive index formula is highly accurate, and indirectly proves that the density distribution of the substance of the electronic electric field is correct.

Introduction

Some researchers maintain that fields themselves constitute an inseparable, fundamental entity [1]. However, the Aharonov–Bohm effect has shown that the electromagnetic potential is even more fundamental than the field [2–6]. Prior studies primarily examined how the electromagnetic potential influences the phase of electrons, neutrons, or electrons in conductive nano-rings via interference experiments. Here, we propose that the electronic electric field arises from a still more fundamental substance [7]. Although its exact nature remains unknown, its density distribution can be experimentally measured. In previous work [8–10], we demonstrated that light behaves as a one-dimensional transverse wave. In this paper, we further show that the inferred density distribution formula for the electronic electric field is accurate.

Theory and evidence

A light wave is one-dimensional transverse wave.

$$v = \sqrt{\frac{G}{\rho}} \quad (1)$$

where G is the shear modulus of the medium, v is the speed of light in the medium, and ρ is the density of the medium, the medium is the substance.

$$\rho = \rho_0 + \frac{K}{r^3} \quad (2)$$

where r is the distance from the optical path to the nearest electron centre in the medium, ρ_0 is the density of the substance in a vacuum. The speed of light in vacuum is c , the refractive index

$n = c/v$, where k and k_1 are coefficients, then

$$n^2 = 1 + \frac{k_1}{r^3} \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) applies to situations with a low electron density, such as those found in gases. Here, d represents the interatomic distance. When the atoms are stationary, the average distance from the light path to the center of each atom is $d/2$. However, when the atoms are moving rapidly and randomly, this average distance decreases to $d/4$. The radius of the electrons' orbit within an atom

is :
$$r_0 = e^2 / (8\pi\epsilon_0 E) = 7.1998/E \text{ (ev)} \quad (4)$$

where E is the first ionizing energy (ev).

When electrons move in a spherical surface of radius r_0 , the electron's contribution to the medium density at the optical path is $k m_e 4\pi r_0^2$, where k is the coefficient and the length units of the r_0 , r and d are Å. m_e is effective electron number in the outer layer. The average distance from the light path to the center of the electron is given by $r = d/4 - r_0$. Therefore, equation (3) becomes:

$$n^2 - 1 = \frac{k \times m_e \times 4\pi (7.1998/E)^2}{(8.349 - 7.1998/E)^3} \quad (5)$$

At 589.3 nm, 0 °C, 1 atm, in the medium of hydrogen gas, $d/4=8.349$, The first ionization energy of hydrogen $E=13.59844$ ev. $r_0=7.1998/13.59844$, $n=1.000139$, In a hydrogen molecule, there are two electrons in the outer layer. When light passes near the molecule, it is affected only by the electron on the right. $m_e = 1$, so $k=0.0377352$.

The first ionization energy of helium is $E=24.58741$ ev. In helium gas, when light passes near a helium atom, it interacts with one electron, while the other electron, located on the opposite side of the atom, is shielded. Substituting $m_e=1$ into (5) gives $n=1.0000389$,

which is larger than the experimental value $(1.000036) + 2.9 \times 10^{-6}$.

It is clear that using formula (5) to calculate the predicted refractive index is highly accurate.

Therefore, formula (5) can effectively serve as a "microscope" to determine the number of electrons in the outer layer of atoms.

In the diatomic molecule the based is the hydrogen:

The first ionization energy of oxygen is $E=13.61806\text{ eV}$. There are four electrons in the outer layer of the oxygen molecule, when the light passes near the oxygen molecule, it is affected by two electrons on the right, $m_e = 2$, substituting in (5) gives $n=1.0002771$, which is larger than the experimental value $(1.0002709) + 6.2 \times 10^{-6}$.

The first ionization energy of chlorine is $E=12.96764\text{ eV}$. There are ten p state electrons in the outer layer of the chlorine molecule; when the light passes near the chlorine molecule, it is affected by five electrons on the right, $m_e = 5$ substituting in (5) gives $n=1.0007716$, which is larger than the experimental value $(1.000773) - 1.4 \times 10^{-6}$.

The first ionization energy of fluorine is $E=17.4228\text{ eV}$. In the outer layer of a fluorine molecule, there are ten ppp-state electrons. Due to the significant shrinkage of the atomic radius (screening effect), when light passes near the fluorine molecule, it is affected by 2.5 electrons on the right. $m_e = 2.5$ substituting in (5) gives $n=1.0002025$, which is larger than the experimental value $(1.000195) + 7.5 \times 10^{-6}$.

The first ionization energy of bromine is $E=11.81381\text{ eV}$. There are ten ppp-state electrons in the outer layer of the bromine molecule. Due to the influence of the second outer electrons, when light passes near the bromine molecule, it is affected by 6 electrons on the right. $m_e=6$ substituting in (5) gives $n=1.001139$, which is larger than the experimental value $(1.001132) + 7.0 \times 10^{-6}$.

The first ionization energy of nitrogen is $E=14.53414\text{ eV}$. There are five electrons in the outer layer of the nitrogen molecule. When light passes near the nitrogen molecule, it is affected by 2.5 electrons on the right. $m_e=2.5$ substituting in (5) gives $n=1.000300$, which is larger than the experimental value $(1.000297) + 3.2 \times 10^{-6}$.

In the monatomic molecules the based is the helium:

The first ionization energy of helium is $E=24.58741\text{ eV}$. In helium gas, when light passes near a helium atom, it is affected by one electron, whereas the other electron on the opposite side of the helium atom is blocked. $m_e=1$. $n=1.000036$, $k=0.0349383$.

The first ionization energy of argon is $E=15.75962\text{ eV}$. There are six p state electrons in the outer layer of the atom, when light passes near the argon atom, it is affected by the three electrons on the right. $m_e=3$ substituting in (5) gives $n=1.0002796$, which is larger than the experimental value $(1.000281) - 1.4 \times 10^{-6}$.

The first ionization energy of neon is $E=21.56454\text{ eV}$. There are six p-state electrons in the outer layer of the neon atom. Due to the significant shrinkage of the atomic radius (screening effect),

when light passes near the neon atom, it is affected by 1.5 electrons on the right.

$m_e=1.5$ substituting in (5) $n=1.00007128$,

which is larger than the experimental value $(1.000067) + 4.3 \times 10^{-6}$.

The first ionization energy of krypton is $E=13.99961$ ev. There are six p-state electrons in the outer layer of the krypton atom. Due to the influence of the second outer electrons, when light passes near the krypton atom, it is affected by 3.5 electrons on the right.

$m_e=3.5$ substituting in (5) gives $n=1.0004225$,

which is larger than the experimental value $(1.000427) - 4.5 \times 10^{-6}$.

The first ionization energy of xenon is $E=12.1298$ ev. There are eight electrons in the outer layer of the xenon atom. Due to the influence of the second outer electrons, when light passes near the xenon atom, it is affected by 4.25 electrons on the right.

$m_e=4.25$, substituting in (5) gives $n=1.000704$,

which is larger than the experimental value $(1.000702) + 2.4 \times 10^{-6}$.

Using formula (5), there are 6 p-electrons in the outer layer of argon (Ar) atoms, as photons can only "see" half the number of p-electrons, resulting in an effective $m_e=3$. The 2s-electrons are not visible due to shielding, so the total visible electrons are not 8.

Following this reasoning, are there 5 p-electrons in the outer layer of chlorine (Cl) atoms? This can be tested using hydrogen chloride (HCl). The ionization energy of HCl is equal to the average of the

ionization energies of hydrogen (H) and chlorine (Cl), $E=13.28304$ eV. The electron number of HCl is the mean $m_e= (1 + 5) / 2=3$ of H and Cl. Formula (5) calculated $n=1.000439$

which is larger than the experimental value $(1.000447) - 8 \times 10^{-6}$.

It proves that 5 p-electrons in the outer layer of Cl atoms are accurate.

Nitric oxide (NO) was used to test whether the outer electron numbers of 2.5 and 2 of N and O atoms were accurate, The ionization energy of nitric oxide equals the average of the ionization energies of N and O, $E=14.0761$ ev, The electron number of NO is the average of the electron number of N and O, $m_e=(2.5+2)/2=2.25$, Formula (5) calculated $n=1.000290$

which is larger than the experimental value $(1.000297) - 7 \times 10^{-6}$.

It proves that 2.5 p-electrons in the outer layer of N and 2 p-electrons in the outer layer of O atoms are accurate.

Air, as a mixture of nitrogen (N), oxygen (O), and trace amounts of argon (Ar), can be used to verify the accuracy of the outer electron numbers of N and O atoms. The ionization energy of air is expected to correspond to the weighted average of the ionization energies of N, O, and Ar,

based on their relative proportions in the mixture. By comparing this calculated mixing value with experimental measurements, the validity of the proposed outer electron numbers for N and O atoms can be tested.

$E = (0.78 * 14.53414 + 0.21 * 13.61806 + 0.0093 * 15.75962) = 14.34299 \text{ eV}$, The outer electron number of the air is a mixed value of the outer electron number of N, O, Ar,

$m_e = (0.78 * 2.5 + 0.21 * 2 + 0.0093 * 3) = 2.3979$, Formula (5) calculated $n = 1.000296$

which is larger than the experimental value $(1.000292) + 4 \times 10^{-6}$.

It proves that 2.5 p-electrons in the outer layer of N and 2 p-electrons in the outer layer of O atoms are accurate.

The errors here are less than 10ppm, so these data strongly prove that Equations (2) and (5) are accurate.

The formula (5) measures that the outer electrons of Ne and F atoms are only half the number of the outer electrons of Ar and Cl atoms, This is a phenomenon that can only after significant shrinkage of the atomic radius (screen). See Table 1 below[11]:

Table 1 Covalent radius and boiling point of the element:

element	He	Ne	Ar	Kr	Xe
covalent radius	0.37	0.62	1.01	1.16	1.36
Δr (Å)		0.39	0.15	0.2	
boiling point	4.23	27.1	87	119.7	165
ΔT (K)	23	60	33	45	
element		F	Cl	Br	I
covalent radius		0.60	1.00	1.17	1.36
Δr (Å)		0.40	0.17	0.19	
boiling point		85	239	332	457
ΔT (K)		154	93	125	

The table shows a significant shrinkage in the covalent radius of neon (Ne) and fluorine (F) atoms, accompanied by a notable decrease in their boiling points.

Conclusion

1. The experimental data described above demonstrate that

$$n^2 - 1 = \frac{k \times m_e \times 4\pi(7.1998/E)^2}{(8.349 - 7.1998/E)^3}$$
 is an exact refractive index formula.

2. The electronic electric field is composed of a substance, this density distribution of the substance is: $\rho = \rho_0 + \frac{K}{r^3}$. The above precise experimental data prove that the density distribution formula of this substance is accurate.

Author contributions

Yc.T. propose a theory; interpreted the data; and substantially revised the manuscript.

Zy.T. interpreted the data and drafted the manuscript.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

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